

ACADEMIC TRAJECTORY OF GRADUATES¹ FROM THE NURSING COURSE OF A PUBLIC UNIVERSITY IN THE STATE OF BAHIA

TRAJETÓRIA ACADÊMICA DE EGRESSOS DO CURSO DE ENFERMAGEM DE UMA UNIVERSIDADE PÚBLICA DO ESTADO DA BAHIA

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Abstract

Introduction: Over the years, the nursing training model, which is strongly marked by a technician logic, has been adapting and reinventing itself with a view to improving the teaching-learning process. **Objective:** To describe the academic trajectory of nursing graduates from a university in the interior of Bahia. **Methodology:** This is an exploratory-descriptive study, based on documents, of a quantitative nature, with the study population being graduates from campus VII of the nursing course at the State University of Bahia. The information was obtained from secondary and documentary sources, with graduates of the nursing course between 2011 and 2019. **Results:** The study population consisted of 194 graduates from UNEB campus VII. The study confirms that the existence of UNEB in the state and its insertion in the northern territory of the state of Bahia demarcates the social relevance associated with the decentralization of universities and the access of the population of this region to public higher education. There is still a predominance of females in the nursing classes; in relation to the race/color variable, blacks predominate in the student body, which reinforces the important role that UNEB plays through its quota policies. The link between students and extension activities is a reality on campus VII. **Conclusion:** The study contributes to finding ways of adopting new teaching methods and technologies that are in line with the demands of the world of work, as well as showing society the university's contribution to training its students.

Keywords: Nursing schools; University education; Graduation.

¹ We refer to students who completed the course and obtained a nursing diploma at the State University of Bahia, campus VII.

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Resumo

Introdução: O modelo formativo de Enfermagem, fortemente marcado pela lógica tecnicista, ao longo dos anos, vem se adaptando e reinventando-se numa perspectiva de aprimoramento no processo de ensino-aprendizagem. **Objetivo:** Descrever a trajetória acadêmica de egressos do curso de Enfermagem de uma universidade do interior da Bahia. **Metodologia:** Estudo exploratório-descritivo, em base documental, de natureza quantitativa, sendo a população do estudo egressos do *campus* VII, do curso de enfermagem da Universidade do Estado da Bahia. As informações foram obtidas de fontes secundárias e documentais, com egressos do curso de enfermagem formados entre 2011 e 2019. **Resultados:** A população do estudo foi de 194 pessoas graduadas na UNEB *campus* VII. O estudo confirma que a existência da UNEB no estado e sua inserção no território norte do estado da Bahia demarca a relevância social associada à descentralização das universidades e o acesso da população dessa região ao ensino superior público. Constata-se a permanência da predominância do sexo feminino nas turmas do curso de enfermagem em relação à variável raça/cor, a negra predomina no corpo estudantil, reforçando o papel importante que a UNEB possui por meio das suas políticas de cotas. A vinculação de estudantes com as atividades de extensão é uma realidade do *campus* VII. **Conclusão:** O estudo contribui, com a elaboração de caminhos, para a adoção de novas modalidades de ensino e tecnologias que estejam conforme as demandas do mundo do trabalho, além de mostrar para a sociedade a contribuição da Universidade na formação de seus discentes.

Palavra-chave: Escolas de enfermagem; Ensino superior; Graduação.

INTRODUCTION

The teaching-learning process in the modern world has generated new forms of knowledge construction. Scientific modernization and technological advances have been taking great proportions for the transformation of epistemological frameworks that align with the world of work. With all this and with the logic of innovation, it is relevant to understand the changes incorporated and transmitted by the educational institutions and mediators of the formal processes of knowledge construction ¹.

Brazilian nursing took the first step towards professionalization in 1880, with the creation of the first nursing school in Brazil ². This moment demarcates the creation of the legal bases of the profession and the attempt of laicization⁶. Over the years, some normative documents for the minimum curriculum existed: 1923; 1949; 1962; 1972; and 1994, which directed and guided the nursing graduate teaching.

⁶ For theorists Maclure and Taylor (2011, p.28): "laicization is a process by which the State asserts its independence in relation to religion". That said, it is necessary to start from the experience of detachment from the religious conditioning attributed to the practice of nursing, since its historical constitution.

The Brazilian Nursing Association — ABEn has as axes: the defense and consolidation of nursing education, scientific research, professional performance as a social practice, essential to social assistance and health, organization and functioning of health services. ABEn analyzed the necessary changes in the formation structure and resulted in the publication of normative documents that regulated the minimum curriculum². These changes follow the socioeconomic-political requests, such as the promulgation of the Federal Constitution of 1988 that implements the Unified Health System (UHS) and, consequently, updates the course for nursing training, health promotion and recovery of diseases. In addition, there was stimulation in the curricular bases and in the essential competences, such as critical thinking, autonomy and the approximation with the health services³.

Nursing training, in a first analysis, leans towards a model that fits the political, social and economic context imposed by the world of work. In the Brazilian context, therefore, it tends to be organized on curricular matrices that value the biomedical model and, consequently, delineate a technical, hospital and curative education⁴.

The new National Education Guidelines and Bases Law (LDB) — Law n. 9,394 of December 20, 1996, incorporated innovations and changes in national education, a restructuring of the graduate courses with the extinction of the minimum curricula and the adoption of specific curricular guidelines for each course. In 2001, the National Curricular Guidelines (DCNs) for nursing graduation, approved by the MEC, determined, among other aspects, the skills and abilities that should be developed in the training of nurses, "generalist, humanistic, critical and reflective training"⁴, with the purpose of problem solving, in health indicators, with comprehensive and multidisciplinary care. With the implementation of the DCNs, nursing training gained a new guise: to be based on a new structuring framework for the education of the profession: the orientation of training to boost the effectiveness of the principles of the Unified Health System (UHS). Furthermore, training should meet the health needs of the population through comprehensive care, and the quality and humanization of care⁵.

With updates to the curriculum, there were new implementations in the teaching-learning relationship that culminated in the reformulations of protocols in classroom practices and a progressive training of health care, obviously aligned with the health system. In an attempt at a more detailed analysis of the context of health training, especially in nursing, it is salutary to consider the ethical-aesthetic-political stakes in the field of health care and the way they provoke the people involved in the process: management, health professionals and workers and users of services. In this way of reflection, it is proposed to consider the humanization policy in health care as a practice that is concerned with respecting users in all their contexts of gender, race, religion/beliefs. Once encouraged to be implemented, it should be studied, practiced and discussed already in the training process of students.

Given the above, it is important to consider that the reformulations of curriculum over the years reflect not only the training, but also the relationships established between professionals, users and managers. The educational development of students, in general, is supported by a professional training oriented to the labor market, capable of integrating theoretical and practical skills, as well as attitudes, ethical values, general and specific knowledge⁶. The labor market, in turn, tends to seek versatile, qualified and committed professionals with institutional logic and nursing practice in different contexts⁷.

Based on these reflections, this article aimed to describe the academic path of graduates from the Nursing course of a university in the interior of Bahia from the perspective of understanding the training process and its alignment with the professional profile foreseen in the labor market of the Brazilian scenario.

The reflection on the academic trajectory of the nursing graduates from a UNEB campus considered their training path, access to teaching, research and extension scholarships, length of stay in the course and pedagogical paths. At first, the research contributes to create a database of information about these trained people, containing the profile of the course and point out advances, potential achieved and those necessary for improvement and improvement in training. Structuring such data during the period that the graduate was in

graduation may allow the university to adapt to the new modes of education, learning methods and technologies that synthesize work life with the purpose of improving teaching curriculum and offering a good quality of teaching that is in accordance with the demands of the world of work. The structuring of these data during the period in which the student was at graduation may allow the university to adapt to the new forms of teaching, learning methods and technologies that synthesize working life with the aim of improving the curriculum and offering a good quality of teaching that is in line with the demands of the world of work.

METHODOLOGY

This is an exploratory-descriptive study, on a documentary basis, of a quantitative nature, and the study population consists of graduates from campus VII, from the nursing course of the University of the State of Bahia.

This campus hosts the Department of Education and has graduate courses in Pedagogy, Mathematics, Nursing, Accounting, Biological Sciences and Theater⁽⁸⁾. In the current curriculum, reformulated in 2018, the bachelor's degree in Nursing has 63 compulsory curricular components taken over the ten academic semesters, that is, five years of course distributed in a full period from Monday to Friday from 8 am to 6 pm⁹. In the previous curriculum matrix, from 2007, there were 48 components of a mandatory nature.

Data collection took place from 2020 to 2021. The study population consisted of 194 graduates between 2011 and 2019. The inclusion criterion adopted was: having completed the course between the period established for the study. Students who did not complete or gave up were excluded.

A search was conducted in the official systems of the University of the State of Bahia (UNEB), in the files that carry information related to the student's entry, the training course, time elapsed until graduation, among other information. Then, the reports provided by the SAGRES system and information bank of scholarship students available on the UNEB page were accessed.

FormSUS was used, a public domain service, with rules defined according to the legislation and the UHS information policy. It was developed to meet the needs of the UHS of partner public agencies, and made available for use by universities and institutions for purposes of public interest. The group of researchers, based on institutional reports, elaborated a database in FormSUS to insert the research data. It was a service that belonged to DATASUS, but, in 2021, it was discontinued by the Brazilian government.

The variables selected for the study were sociodemographic data, arranged in chart 1 and the profile of the graduate's education, which includes the time to complete the course, percentage of dropout and trajectory during graduation, concerning participation in extension projects, scientific initiation projects, monitoring, volunteering in projects or enjoyment of some type of aid.

Chart 1: Variables according to the student's sociodemographic profile.

VARIABLES	CATEGORIZATION
Sex	Male; female
Age group in years	17-19 years; 20-29; 30-39; 40-44
Place of residence	Antônio Gonçalves; Amélia Rodrigues; Andorinha; Barrocas; Caldeirão Grande; Campo Formoso; Cansanção; Capim Grosso; Conceição do Coité; Euclides da Cunha; Feira de Santana; Filadélfia; Ipirá; Irecê; Itabuna; Itiúba; Jacobina; Jaguarari; Juazeiro; Miguel Calmon; Monte Santo; Pé de Serra; Petrolina; Pindobaçu; Ponto Novo; Queimadas; Quixabeira; Retirolândia; Riachão do Jacuípe; Rodelas; Salvador; Santa Luz; Senhor do Bonfim; Serrinha; Serrolândia; Tucano; Uauá; Uibaí; Umburanas; Valença; Várzea Nova; Xique-Xique
Race/Color	Black; Brown; White; Yellow; Indigenous; Missing Data
Type of admission	Entrance exam; Sisu; ENEM; Internal; external transfer; Quota or non-quota; Missing Data

Source: Created by the authors.

The data were collected based on the reports available from the university, which were entered in FormSUS through the enrollment number of the graduate to preserve their identification, being this set of numbers converted/tabulated in an Excel spreadsheet - Microsoft Office 2016 for more appropriate management and greater organization of the data obtained, for later transfer for analysis in the STATA® software, version 14. A choropleth scale map was created by frequency, using as a unit the number of people analyzed. The map was created with TABWIN, an application used to quickly tabulate data and cross-reference information, enabling managers, students and the general public to obtain diverse information within the UHS, and is important in the management of health policies

10.

Data analysis was performed using descriptive statistics, with absolute and relative data. The results were grouped and presented in the form of charts and tables.

The study was not submitted to the Research Ethics Committee because it is a documentary research with secondary data available from the course and on the university website. However, all ethical precepts were followed in the processing, analysis and disclosure of the study data.

RESULTS

One hundred and ninety-four individuals make up the database of this research, which mostly lived in the cities of Bahia (only one lived in Petrolina-PE). Regarding the city of origin of the graduates at the beginning of the course: they come from Senhor do Bonfim (26.8% n=54); from Jacobina (10.31% n=19); from Campo Formoso (8.25% n=16); and from Juazeiro and Conceição do Coité, both with 6.19% (n=12). The other cities presented percentages between 0.51% (n=1) and 5.67% (n=11) (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Choropleth map of the distribution of the number of students by cities of origin of graduates from the University of the State of Bahia, upon admission, from 2011 to 2019.

Source: Tabwin, 2011-2019. Unit: number of people

Of the 194 graduates, 87.63% (n=170) were female, and 12.37% (n=24), male. As for the age group of access to graduation, there is predominance of 20 - 29 years (52.58% n=104), followed by 17 - 19 years (38.14% n=74). Despite the percentages, 8.25% (n=16) of the graduates belonged to the 30 - 39 years group, and 1.03% (n=3), to the 40 - 49 years group.

Regarding the variable race/color, the black population predominated, with 48.45% (N=94), of which 39.69% are black people (N=77), and 8.76% self-declared as brown (N=17). The other records indicate percentages of white people 3.61% (N=7), indigenous people 3.09% (N=06) and yellow people 0.52% (N=01). It is also noteworthy that 44.33% (N=86) of the information were missing.

Table 1 shows the percentages related to the form of admission of students. It is noteworthy that UNEB currently has as admission modalities vacancies for candidates not opting quotas, called vestibular (1), vacancies for black people, represented in the table below as vestibular (2), other vacancies for indigenous, *Quilombola* people, gypsies, autistic people, high abilities; transsexuals, transvestites and transgender, denominated in the table as vestibular (3).

Table 1 – Admission method for nursing graduates from the University of the State of Bahia, campus VII, from 2011 to 2019.

Type of admission [1]	N	%
Entrance exam (1)	90	46,39
Entrance exam (2)	71	36,60
Entrance exam (3)	5	2,58
External transfer	15	7,70
Internal transfer	2	1,03
ENEM	7	3,61
Other	4	2,06

Source: Data bank.

The data reveal that most people, in the period studied, entered the UNEB by vestibular system. Of these, 46.39% (n=90) people opted for broad competition. The candidates opting for the vacancies for black people, classified as vestibular (2), represented 36.60% (n=71). Other percentages, still related to the form of admission, are related to external transfer, 7.70% (n=15), and 2.58% (n=5) entered by the other vacancies for indigenous people, 3.61% (n=7) through ENEM, 1.03% (n=2) people who opted for internal transfer, and 2.06% (n = 4), who accessed higher education by another form of admission.

Concerning the permanence of these students in the course, table 3 relates the information about the form of admission with benefit of Permanence Assistance programs. It is possible to observe the demarcated absence of information. Missing data can demonstrate the fragility of a student assistance

policy at the university in the period studied. The policies of permanence in a university are important instruments that contribute to the quality of training of students. For this reason, it was decided to keep the information in this article. The survey data reveal that, regarding the non-use of permanence-aid, 29 people, representing 14.72% of graduates. Related to this quantity, 19.57% were people entering by broad competition, and 11.11% by quota system.

Table 2 – Relationship between admission method and Permanence Assistance programs for nursing graduates from the University of the State of Bahia, campus VII, from 2011 to 2019.

Type of admission	Permanence aid N(%)		
	Yes	No	No information
Entrance exam (1)	1 (1,0%)	18 (19,5%)	73 (79,3%)
Entrance exam (2)	1 (1,3%)	8 (11,1%)	60 (87,5%)
Entrance exam (3)	-	-	5 (100,0%)
External transfer	-*	1 (6,6%)	14 (93,3%)
Internal transfer	-	-	2 (100,0%)
ENEM	-	1 (14,2%)	3 (75,0%)
Other	-	1 (25,0%)	3 (75,0%)
Total	2 (1.0%)	29 (14.7%)	163 (84.3%)

* Data that obtained 0.0% and the number of people. **Source:** Data bank.

Table 3 lists the form of admission with the linking of teaching, extension and scientific initiation monitoring projects.

Table 3 – Relationship between the form of admission and linking of teaching, research and extension monitoring scholarships for nursing graduates from the University of the State of Bahia, campus VII, in the period from 2011 to 2019.

Form of admission	Teaching monitoring scholarship			Research Initiation Scholarship		Extension monitoring scholarship		
	Yes	No	No inform.	Yes	No	Yes	No	No inform.
Entrance exam (1)	26 (28,2%)	49 (53,2%)	17 (18,4%)	27 (29,3%)	65 (70,6%)	27 (29,3%)	50 (54,3%)	15 (16,3%)
Entrance exam (2)	12 (16,6%)	35 (48,6%)	25 (34,7%)	10 (13,8%)	62 (86,1%)	15 (20,8%)	32 (44,4%)	25 (34,7%)
Entrance exam (3)	-*	2 (40,0%)	3 (60,0%)	-	5 (100%)	-	2 (40,0%)	3 (60,0%)
External transfer	1 (6,6%)	7 (46,6%)	7 (46,6%)	3 (20,0%)	12 (80,0%)	4 (26,6%)	5 (33,3%)	6 (40,0%)
Internal transfer	1 (50,0%)	1 (50,0%)	-	-	2 (100,0%)	2 (100,0%)	-	-
ENEM	1 (14,2%)	4 (57,1%)	2 (28,5%)	4 (57,1%)	3 (42,8%)	4 (57,1%)	1 (14,2%)	2 (28,5%)
Other	-	2 (50,0%)	2 (50,0%)	-	4 (100,0%)	-	2 (50,0%)	2 (50,0%)
Total	41 (20,8%)	100 (50,7%)	56 (28,4%)	44 (22,3%)	153 (77,6%)	52 (26,4%)	92 (46,7%)	53 (26,9%)

* Data that obtained 0.0% and the number of people. **Source:** Data bank.

Based on the data presented in the table, it is confirmed that, in the period studied, the graduates were mostly linked to extension scholarships (26.40%). In relation to the data on research activities, it is possible to verify that there is no lack of information, justifying the absence of the column "no information". The reality of data organization at the university can justify the quantity of information lost. Another necessary aspect to be considered is that the study includes the first years of implementation of the course, a phase in which there are numerous challenges, including data management or hiring professors, key figures for the scholarship application.

The departments have peculiar characteristics in data management, but, regarding the research demands, the SONIC system standardizes the methods of data linkage throughout UNEB, as well as in the monitoring of students and professors, possibility of systematization and better organization of the data. In relation to extension and teaching projects, the monitoring of the grants is under the responsibility of departments, Research and Extension Centers and collegiate. The absence of information weakens the possibility of understanding the data related to the path experienced in teaching.

DISCUSSION

Regarding the multicampi character of UNEB, it is worth reflecting on the social relevance associated with the decentralization of universities. This reality makes visible a challenge in the creation and consolidation to assist 15 million people from Bahia in the semi-arid territory. Regarding UNEB and its multicampi structure, the importance of its existence in the interior of Bahia is noteworthy. Authors argue about the relevance of the university in the interior in some requirements ¹¹:

- 1) a state education system to be complete covers from pre-school education, through elementary, high school, college to post-graduation;
- 2) a state higher education relates to the territorial space by cultural identity, and can be organized by unicampus or multicampi universities;
- and 3) a college or university installed in an interior urban center is a factor of progress by adding laboratories, libraries, equipment and facilities changing and enriching the urban community ^{11:3}.

It is possible to understand that, since the creation of UNEB, its structure, strategies and/or objectives, in its form of multicampi, had to do precisely with giving conditions to less favored communities. UNEB was founded in Bahia and is based on the idea of reflecting its regions, with blackness, with the backlands, with poverty, with problems of education, food and health ¹². This enabled a democracy in access to public and free higher education, reducing in expression the social inequality, which allow the backcountry people in a situation of poverty and without access to universities of large urban centers to have this access without having to move to major capitals. The map 01 brought in the results confirms the local relevance of the existence of the university in the territory.

The UNEB Nursing course, campus VII, was created on April 6, 2006, and approved in resolution CONSU 367/2006. The graduation aims to train nurses in a critical, reflective, scientific and humanistic perspective, preparing professionals to work in the area of assistance, management, research and teaching. The first class began in 2007.2 with 30 incoming students, of which 23 completed the minimum time of the course in the academic semester 2011.2 and, between 2011 and 2019, 194 students graduated.

The entrance to the university, from 2007.2, occurred only through the vestibular exam. In the same year 50 vacancies were offered. In 2008.2, 2009.2 and 2010.1 there were 30 vacancies. From 2011.1 the entry into UNEB occurred, not only by vestibular exam, but also through the Unified Selection System (SiSU). SiSU is the computerized system of the Ministry of Education, in which public higher education institutions offer vacancies for candidates participating in the National High School Exam (ENEM).

The vacancies at UNEB guarantee for broad competition, aimed at quota candidates and other vacancies: 60% of the vacancies for non-administered candidates; 40% of the vacancies for black candidates; 5% of vacancies for indigenous candidates 5% of vacancies for *Quilombola* candidates; 5% of vacancies for gypsy candidates; 5% of vacancies for candidates with disabilities, autism spectrum disorder and high abilities; and 5% for transsexual, transvestite and transgender candidates(s) ¹³.

Regarding the debate on gender, as pointed out in table 01, it is understood to be a relevant theme in nursing, especially by the history of its training process as a profession. According to data from the Federal Nursing Council, 84.6% of nursing professionals are women¹⁴. In a historical context, with European and Western cut, care is an attribution mostly assumed by charitable women and linked to the church. This care was attributed to the woman precisely because it associates her to a maternal figure, possessing healing knowledge passed from mother to daughter⁴. The figures of Florence Nightingale and Anna Nery as reference personalities in nursing also signal the female gender as the basis for the profession. This is reflected, then, to the present day, in the female predominance in nursing. One cannot yet disregard the vulnerabilities that the woman, in her existence, carries in society. The intersection between gender and profession demarcates aspects that may reflect in advances and setbacks of the profession.

The idea of volunteering, benevolence and charity in the care provided by nursing reflects on the consolidation of the profession and the social ideology linked to the practices. It is possible to associate that the historical-social construction of the profession is currently reflected, including in the marked persistent devaluation. For this devaluation, extra working hours are included in COFEN (2015):

With professional links that accumulate at least 18 hours of daily work, these women still face the domestic journey when caring for their home, partner and children. However, this extra journey is not effectively recognized as not publicly visible¹⁴.

It is indisputable the historical struggle for recognition and appreciation both professional as in fair workload and wages appropriate to the profession. Currently, after years of struggle, Bill 2,564 of 2020 was approved, amending Law n. 7,498, of June 25, 1986, to institute the national wage floor of the Nurse, Nursing Technician, Nursing Assistant and Midwife¹⁵.

In relation to the population studied at UNEB, it is worth mentioning that, even if the highest percentage of admission of the study population was broad competition (see table 02), the data presented reveal the predominance of black graduates at UNEB. This may point to a process of change in the reality of Brazilian higher education, confirmed in the study on the Nursing Profile in Brazil.

The research on the Nursing Profile in Brazil, one of the broadest diagnoses about the nursing profession performed in Latin America, shows that Brazilian nursing is composed of 53% of black people¹².

Regarding the policies of permanence and the modality of entry into the course (table 3), it is remarkable to perceive the fragility in the provision of data by the amount — almost null — of students contemplated with an aid that would allow them to stay at the university. It is noteworthy that the information of this research was obtained from public data, therefore, on the aid-permanence, the university does not provide on its public website transparent information about this aspect. Another factor that marks such results is the period in which these student assistance policies were created. The *Mais Futuro* Program, for example, which benefits students regularly enrolled in face-to-face graduate courses at the four state universities in the state of Bahia, was created in 2016, thus not contemplating the students included in the study.

Regarding the relationship between the type of scholarships and the form of admission (table 4), it can be observed that, among those awarded some type of scholarship in teaching, research and extension in the course, the percentage was below 50%. On this point, one of the hypotheses of data fragility may be associated with the time of implementation of the course and its structuring process, which there was no time to guarantee the students of the campus. Moreover, it may be linked to the data collection devices of this research, when using public domain data. For a better analysis of this relationship, it would be necessary to have direct contact with the sectors or with the own graduate. The relevance of articulating the scholarships with the type of admission is in the possibility of analyzing the association of incoming students by the quota system, for example, and the support received by the university in their permanence until graduation.

Despite the fragility of some data, it is worth mentioning that table 4 reveals that the percentage of students linked to some type of scholarship: teaching, research and extension were admitted by broad competition. The link with the extension activities stood out, drawing a reality of campus VII. Reflecting on these data and the importance of these scholarship modalities, especially extension, reveals a culture of creating a link between university and community, by allowing extensionist actions that provide support to the population in exchange for graduates' practical, critical and scientific knowledge.

The process of training the nursing professional indeed goes through not only changes by the very dialectical character of society, but also a search for adaptation to the world of work. This, to some extent, enables new measures in the teaching-learning process and technological means for better training of critical, humanistic and reflective nurses.

FINAL THOUGHTS

The description of the academic course of Nursing graduates first allowed the understanding of the impact of the university in the territory of its insertion. In its proposal of multicampi and inclusive political actions, UNEB proposes to provide opportunities for those in rural areas and those in conditions of social vulnerability to have access to public and quality higher education, becoming the largest public university in the state of Bahia.

The research revealed some challenges faced by the institution in ensuring data transparency.

The research data confirm that black people, female, are the majority of UNEB graduates. In the period studied, information on the reality of student permanence policy was expressively non-existent, making it impossible to analyze this student right in depth.

The teaching, research and extension monitoring scholarships linked to the students of the studied reality demonstrate the impact of the university in the territory. The data also revealed the significant character of university extension on campus.

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